

End-to-end integration, a solution during COVID-19?

**Wouter
Eversdijk**

w.b.eversdijk@tilburguniversity.edu

**Julie
Heijs**

j.f.heijs@tilburguniversity.edu

**Vita
de Jong**

v.v.dejong@tilburguniversity.edu

**Tara
Willems**

t.j.p.willems@tilburguniversity.edu

**Fleur
Wirken**

f.e.j.m.wirken@tilburguniversity.edu

ABSTRACT

This document concerns a short review of the impact of COVID-19 in the Dutch logistics sector. Specifically, it focuses on the well known JIT method. JIT relies on the ability within a supply chain to respond directly to a request from the following player in the chain, relying on knowledge from previous orders. The crisis brings unpredictable orders which means that the players in the chain do not have the needed resources. End-to-End Integration looks like a solution, but the fast implementation brings not only advantages. The analysis within this document looks at the governance, process integration, and security of such change in the chain. This digital transformation of the chain already had clear benefits, but it is unclear whether these build up against the risk that a fast implementation during a crisis brings.

Keywords

COVID-19, Logistics, Just-in-Time, end-to-end Integration, Business Process

INTRODUCTION

Searches for terms such as ‘contactless’ increased over 7-times between November 2019 and late April 2020. Entire countries went into lock-down, sporting events were fully canceled and over 2 million infections were detected, and these numbers are currently, October 2020, still rising. 2019 and 2020 can be called the years of COVID-19. This pandemic has giant consequences, affecting every industry forcing them to respond with extraordinary speed and vigor. Businesses are forced into the rapid development of their digital technologies to help reduce face-to-face interactions.

The following report will focus on the effects that COVID-19 has on the digital transformation of Small Medium Enterprises

(SMEs) that work within the logistical sector. The logistical sector plays an important part in the COVID-19 crisis.

Nowadays, countries are dependent on the logistics sector for the supply of goods and basic necessities of life. With the current high demands of customers and the availability of the same or next day delivery, the supply chain needs to work efficiently at all times. For this reason, more companies are implementing the Just-in-Time method as part of Last-Mile Delivery. During the first big COVID-19 outbreak in March 2020, entire countries were in lock-down as well as a large part of the logistics inflow. Therefore, the delivery reliability in the entire logistics sector decreased, resulting in the failure of the Just-in-Time method.

In the following report, we will research ways the logistical sector can recover and continue to operate in the time of the COVID-19 outbreak. Focusing on the digital transformation of companies.

RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

Our research is about the logistical sector focusing on transport and logistics. During the COVID-19 outbreak, companies need to find ways to innovate in the way they do business. One of the ways companies can innovate is by moving to the JIT method. JIT stands for the Just-in-Time method. It is a product of lean-management with the goal of delivering materials just in time when it is necessary, making big stocks obsolete. For companies to make use of this way of doing business, they will need to undergo a digital transformation. In the past this was entirely voluntary but due to COVID-19 companies being forced into digital transformation the objective of this report is to help companies give insights into how they approach this digital transformation and what the JIT method means during a crisis like COVID-19.

The research question that follows is: “How does the implementation of the Just-in-Time method during a crisis affect IT Governance, Business

Process Integration, and Cybersecurity of a Small Medium Enterprises supply chain?" We will go into the steps necessary, the pros and cons, how these concepts influence each other, and what a crisis does to JIT delivery.

RESEARCH APPROACH

For our report, we will first focus on doing a literature review with the main goal being to broaden the knowledge about the Dutch logistical sector and how the COVID-19 outbreak affected this industry. Furthermore, we will dive into the JIT method, what does it mean? What are the pros and cons? How to successfully implement this technique? The next aspect is the digital transformation of a company with the ultimate goal being the combination of the JIT method and digital transformation. The final report should be insightful for people who work or have a lot to do with small or medium enterprises (SMEs) in the Dutch logistical sector during the COVID-19 outbreak.

For each of these different aspects, we will do a literary review and summarize the most important "lessons learned". We will mainly focus on academic papers however due to the newness of COVID-19 this will be supplemented by non-academic sources.

Finally, we will focus on the future, how will companies in the Dutch logistical sector affect the future post-pandemic society.

LOGISTICS & TRANSPORT

One of the biggest sectors in The Netherlands is the Transport and Logistics sector. The Netherlands is an important international hub that connects countries all over the world. Many export products cross The Netherlands during their journey. Products can be transferred between different modalities such as air freight, maritime freight, pipelines, road- and railways. Transport and logistics are a broad concept that involves many companies and products. A distinction can be made between the kind of goods that are transported; general cargo, bulk, cars, refrigerated goods, animals, exceptional sizes, and dangerous goods. Within this paper, the focus lies on general cargo, which has maximum standard sizes and normal circumstances wherein the products can be transported.

Miller (2020) oversees different trends that will reshape the logistics industry in the coming years. Firstly, business trends have a huge impact on the matter. Customers' expectations are getting

higher. They want their goods faster, lower delivery costs, and there is an increasing demand for customized goods. The trends 'Last-Mile deliveries' and 'localizing warehouses' arise from these desires in the market. Secondly, social trends such as urbanization and sustainability will influence the market in the future. Lastly, and maybe the most influential section is the technological trends that will reshape the logistics industry. Inventions such as autonomous vehicles, platooning technologies, and electric or hybrid trucks provide a reduction in costs, increasing efficiency, and a higher degree of sustainability. Other technological trends that influence the logistics sector are Customer-Facing APIS, AI, and Big Data, and Drones, and Robotics.

An interesting method that is implemented more often in the supply chains of big companies is the Just-in-Time method, also known as JIT. JIT is the method used within Last-Mile Deliveries and which arose because of customers' expectations of faster delivery times such as same-day or 48-hour deliveries. The inventory management method establishes that materials and other goods are scheduled exactly available in the manufacturing process when needed. The JIT inventory system is a management strategy that aligns raw-material orders from suppliers directly with production schedules. Companies employ this inventory strategy to increase efficiency and decrease waste by receiving goods only as they are needed in the production process, thereby reducing inventory costs. This method requires that producers can accurately forecast demand (Tajari, 2018). The JIT is an inventory strategy where materials are only ordered and received as they are needed in the production process. The goal is to lower the inventory (costs) and reliably deliver the end-products exactly on the desired moment at the customer. The JIT method is part of Total Quality Management in which the goal is to reduce waste in the supply chain. Wherein waste is defined as undesirable costs, time, and other inefficiencies.

In more detail, the JIT method system has several advantages and disadvantages. The advantages are the reduced costs of storing raw materials. There is less investment in raw materials and JIT speeds up the manufacturing process as the material is available readily. It also eliminates the lead time and helps shorter production runs. And in the end, it eliminates wastage in terms of time, inventory, and transportation. The disadvantages are that JIT can lead to potential supply chain destruction and manufacturers have no margin to make any errors because the goods have to be delivered right away. Another point of disadvantage is that JIT makes the supply chain less flexible, it is unable to meet any unexpected order from the customer. Plus there is no time for renegotiation

with customers (Tajari, 2018).

Digital globalization is defined by flows of data and information. The current crisis COVID-19 is causing a strong shift of businesses towards digital transformation. In the process of digitization of countries and companies, global data flows are surging and digital platforms are allowing countries and small companies to participate. Many advantages come along with digitization in big data, predictive analytics, and artificial intelligence. Also, the Internet of Things (IoT) exploits after this shift towards digitization. IoT includes smart and connected devices that create and manage data as it makes a business interactive. In this way, companies can shift from a centralized production model to a more decentralized intelligent and connected model (Schilirò, 2020). For the JIT method, this can lead to chances but also risks. This analysis will be made in chapter 5 Analysis.

To know what the effect of COVID-19 is on JIT, the definition of crisis, like COVID-19, should be mentioned. According to the Merriam-Webster dictionary (Crisis, 2020), a crisis can be defined as “an unstable or crucial time or state of affairs in which a decisive change is impending” and “a situation that has reached a critical phase.”. A crisis can harm businesses, but can also be seen as an opportunity. According to the research of Pedersen and Ritter (2020), some capabilities that are considered costly, complex, and unproductive before the crisis became important after the crisis hit. One of the examples that they mention is excess capacity in warehouses. An important topic for businesses in the future is the level of preparedness that they need to reach. Not only to keep the business running, but also for investors that are more aware of the risks that companies endure when facing a crisis. Preparedness is not without costs like investments in resources. “Therefore, there will be a new rationale for organizations to rethink their risk-management approaches and the solutions in which they invest to address those risks.” (Pedersen & Ritter, 2020).

Concluding, one of the main advantages of the JIT method is the fact that the parties in the supply chain do not need storage, and therefore reduce costs. But, with the influence of COVID-19, an unstable time came that influenced the chain. According to several reports from the logistics sector (Nieuws - Transport & Logistiek | Consultancy.nl, 2020), flexibility and resilience have been of high importance. The focus of this report is to find a solution to reach flexibility and resilience while keeping the main advantages of the JIT method. A possible solution for this is end-to-end integration from the systems in the chain. In the next chapter, an analysis is made describing the IT

Governance, Business Process Integration, and Cyber Security of the situation pre- and post COVID-19.

ANALYSIS

IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing

The core IT Governance aspects from the Governance Design Matrix from Weill (2004) are used to evaluate the JIT method in a total supply chain. Moreover, has the current crisis COVID-19 changed the environment, and did it influence the IT Governance? This question will be handled within this paragraph.

In the situation before COVID-19, the companies that are working together in the supply chain all have their own governance and make business and IT decisions by themselves. The archetype they execute is Business Monarchy, wherein the top managers of each company makes decisions for their own business. All companies are responsible for their own part of the supply chain. Agreements between the different companies are made about when and where materials, semi-finished products, and products must be located in the chain. Besides business decisions also IT decisions are made separately by each company. There is no shared system or real-time communication between the companies. When problems arise or delays occur by one of the first companies of the chain, companies later on in the chain cannot quickly react to the problems because little information between the companies is shared. The little information that is shared between companies within the chain is mostly between the company upfront and after the company where the processing step is made.

The crisis COVID-19 caused a change in the governance structure. JIT is all about aligning productions with other companies in the chain to guarantee delivery reliability. Because of the current crisis, the way decisions are made has to change too. Especially now with this crisis, companies need to know every possible delay or minuscule change that can lead to lower delivery reliability. To tackle this issue and to make sure all the systems are accurate and connected with other companies, IT needs to play a big factor in organizing the systems. Taken this into account, the governance archetype needs to move from Business Monarchy to Federal. The keyword for this change is end-to-end integration. The integration of companies is determined in the IT Architecture principle. The whole supply chain needs to know what the status of the other companies is. So, where they are standing in the production process and how the delivery time and

production time is and if it has changed because of the crisis. In this way, companies in the supply chain can organize and anticipate unforeseen issues. The fact that IT needs to play a bigger role, the IT executives also need a saying in the governance to optimize the data and information flow.

Business Process Integration

The business processes need to change due to the COVID-19 crisis. To see what kind of digital transformation companies with the JIT method go through, the pre- and post COVID-19 business processes are explained. The transformation that all the companies should go through is to realize an end-to-end integrated process. In the JIT method, companies use carefully streamlined procedures for the exchange of information. Many companies already work together with all the other companies in the supply chain, realizing efficiency and cost reduction (Themistocleous et al., 2002). One way of realizing this is when all of the players in the chain use electronic data interchange (EDI). EDI is structured data that can be used to transfer information about orders and confirmations. Using EDI, the flow of information is streamlined and the parties are up-to-date about the status and orders in a supply chain. A possible effect when companies use EDI can be a reduction in costs and an increase in efficiency. EDI is not simply a mechanism for exporting data from one system to another, but it also realizes interaction between systems. When a new trading partner is added, they need to write software to translate their own documents into the standardized file formats that EDI uses according to their protocol (Papazoglou & Ribbers, 2006).

EDI looks like the ideal situation to manage a supply chain and integrate with all the companies in the chain. But, in the current situation, many organizations do not use EDI. "EDI is pretty popular in the supply chain industry, with somewhere between 59 and 85% of companies adopting the technology. But this still means up to 41% of companies are using manual processes (O'Shaughnessy, 2019). The EDI is a concept that is created by large companies and for large companies. SME companies do not have the resources to join with this concept. According to the statistics of CBS (2020), in Q1 of 2020, there were 900 companies in the sector of transport and storage with more than 100 employees. More than 47000 had less than 100 employees. With these numbers, one can state that there are more SMEs than large companies. The result is a supply chain like the fictive one visualized in figure 1.

Figure 1. Current Integration Overview

In Figure 1 the dotted lines indicate the possibility to share product information through EDI.

One of the solutions to overcome the crisis is that companies need to be integrated from end-to-end of the supply chain process. This means that all of the companies in a supply chain need to have EDI. Figure 2 shows the situation that enables companies to reach delivery reliability as before COVID-19.

Figure 2. End-to-End Integration Overview

To realize this, the SMEs in the chain needs to be able to use EDI. With this concept, they can communicate with all other parties in the chain and be up-to-date about the order and delays in the order. By doing this, companies strengthen their relationships and collaborate at an inter-organizational level, there will be more links between companies that increases management and coordination efforts. Post COVID-19 this means that they can communicate adjustments in order faster, which makes their JIT method more flexible.

Cyber Security

The digital transformation in the Dutch logistics and transport sector has affected security and in particular cybersecurity. More people are relying on technology and therefore the risk profile changes. As described before, for the JIT method to work in times of crisis companies have to consider

implementing EDI in the supply chain. When implementing EDI, changes have to be made in the codes of the company's systems. When changing code in this short amount of time, the cyber risks have to be considered. Whether it is safe and there is no chance of being hacked. Also, you have to rely on other company's security measures in the supply chain.

Helbing (2013) finds that among others supply chains and information and communication systems have become vulnerable on a planetary scale. The research states that the higher risks are implied by networks of networks, in other words by the coupling of different kinds of systems. In fact, new vulnerabilities result from the increasing interdependencies between our energy, food and water systems, global supply chains, communication, and financial systems, ecosystems, and climate. The World Economic Forum has described this situation as a hyper-connected world, and we, therefore, refer to the associated risks as 'hyper-risks'. These hyper-risks apply when looking at the supply chain. Also, important to mention is that the supply chain is lagging behind in terms of cybersecurity. From a business perspective, managers often still look at the company itself instead of the whole (supply) chain. Resulting in more general risks that apply to the whole supply chain, because they are not managed within the whole supply chain.

To map out all the risks concerning cybersecurity in the supply chains, a risk matrix is made. This table shows the risks and solutions to minimize these risks. Also, a risk analysis is made to see if the controls will help to minimize the risks. An in-depth explanation of the risk analysis and risk matrix can be found in the appendix 1. The most important risks found were Phishing, Mallware and Ransomware. Solutions to cope with these risks are educating employees, creating awareness and investing in protecting software. In today's digital world if no caution is to be taken the likelihood of a security breach is almost certain. Therefore we highly recommend investing time and resources in educating and protecting employees to these threats. Finally the most important lessons learned from the risk matrix is that the impact of a risk will remain the same but with the right precautions the likelihood of an attack can be significantly reduced.

DISCUSSION & CONCLUSION

In this section, the different views and discussion points of the analysis will be evaluated. During the analysis, two situations have been identified. JIT method of companies before and after COVID-19.

The digital transformation that results from the current COVID-19 pandemic makes for a quick change that many people beforehand do not find possible. With these changes and improvements in the sector, also a lot of challenges and risks arise. Companies that follow the JIT method need to think about whether to invest or not in new technologies and new methods. Implementing EDI will result in faster and more flexible communication, but will the investment be worth it in the long term? The organizations that implement the EDI will also face major issues concerning governance, and security. The main selling point of companies in this sector is their delivery reliability. Due to the pandemic, this cannot always be ensured anymore. The digital transformation already started before COVID-19, the crisis only speeded up the importance and therefore the implementation. The importance of end-to-end integration was already visible and has only become more clear. Nevertheless, the implementation has to be done in such a way that it can last and that the risks that come with the integration are taken under consideration. For IT Governance and Strategic Sourcing, this means a change in the appointment of responsibilities for the IT Architecture. It is unclear if, when this is done within such a short time frame, the new responsibilities for decision rights and output are well implemented without risks. For Business Process Integration, the implementation of EDI brings large investments for SMEs. Not only the concept of EDI needs a large investment, but the security of the EDI needs also financial resources for implementation. The more companies in the supply chain, the more security risks when integrating with other companies. Whether or not EDI is a solution for the currently failing JIT, depends on the (financial) resources and knowledge of the companies within the supply chain.

The research and analysis were done in a short time frame. This leads to a brief analysis that may not have covered all aspects of the subject. Furthermore, this research is only done by literature research and no practical research was applied. It became clear that little research on this specific topic was available. Considering this pandemic and the digital transformation resulting from this is a quite new development, it is understandable that not much research has been done yet.

The advice for further research into this topic is to conduct a case study where the literature study can be tested. A case study can provide more details about the current situation, and if the changes recommended by this research do work in practice.

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Appendix 1 Risk matrix

Primary process	Risk	Rank	Likelihood (1-5) * Impact (1-5)	New Controls	*Revised Likelihood (1-5) * Impact (1-5)
IT-strategy	R1: Connectivity Rush	#3	3 * 3 = 9	Consideration before implementation	2 * 3 = 6
Operations	R2: Untrained Staff	#2	4 * 4 = 16	Train staff	2 * 4 = 8
IT-development	R3: No Cybersecurity plan	#4	2 * 3 = 6	Invest in Cybersecurity plan	1 * 3 = 3
IT-maintenance	R4: Legacy Devices	#4	2 * 3 = 6	Isolate legacy devices	1 * 3 = 3
Logistical Operations	R5: Third-party vulnerabilities	#3	3 * 3 = 9	Increase visibility, enforce agreed cybersecurity standards	2 * 3 = 6
Operations	R6: Ransomware / Malware	#1	5 * 4 = 20	Educate, invest in software	3 * 4 = 12
Operations	R7: Phishing	#1	5 * 4 = 20	Educate, invest in software	3 * 4 = 12
IT-development	R8: Increase use of Cloud Computing	#3	3 * 3 = 9	Invest in secure cloud solutions	2 * 3 = 6